

ePIC Style Guidelines

Version 1.0 (July 2025)

Figure Style Guidelines

Please follow the guidelines below to help make sure your figures are clear and easy to read for both presentations and papers.

- Include the appropriate ePIC tag, preferably in the upper left corner of the figure.
- The ePIC logo, if you choose to include one on a figure in presentations, should be of small to moderate size in a noticeable area, not faded or used as a watermark.
- List necessary information, such as collision system and energy, beam polarization if any, process of interest, etc.
- Format: vector graphic format (PDF preferred), where lines and text have not been rendered.
- Axis:
 - Axes should be labeled including their units.
 - Axis labels should not extend off of the canvas (this often happens for superscripts and subscripts) and that the text doesn't run into the axis tick marks.
 - Reduce axis ranges as much as reasonably possible.
 - Use the member function `TAxis::SetDecimals()` to ensure that all tick mark labels are printed to the same precision, e.g., 0.8 1.0 1.2 ... instead of 0.8 1 1.2 ...
- Color:
 - Use both color and symbol styles to indicate different sets of data. This is because while for many people red/blue is easily distinguishable some people are color blind and cannot differentiate. Using different symbol styles also means data points can be distinguished when printed black and white.
 - Choose color pairings other than red/blue for better contrast.
 - Do not use yellow, light green, or light blue - it may look good on your screen but they do not project well.
- Font: lettering should be in a sans-serif typeface, preferably Helvetica or Arial

- Text size: use a minimum text size of 0.04 in ROOT. If possible, use 0.06 for axis label and title.
 - For presentations, all lettering should be visible from the back of an auditorium for a figure filling 1/4 of the area of the screen.
- Use a clear background with unbroken lines and black-white contrast as much as possible.
- Avoid small open symbols that may "fill in", small dots and decimal points, and shading or cross-hatching that is not coarse enough to show up when printed.
- Avoid excessive empty space in the figures.

A template for making ePIC figures can be found here:

<https://zenodo.org/records/16615455>

Tips for Slides

- Consider the structure of your talk and your audience carefully. People outside the ePIC Collaboration are most interested in the physics content of your presentation, and will assume that the technical details are correct if you have satisfied ePIC policies to present these results in a public forum.
- Present the 10,000 ft view of your analysis and how it connects to ePIC goals in the introductory slides.
- Explain your methodology clearly; minimize discussion of event selection; be clear about what uncertainties are being shown, and discuss final results and their implications.
- Showing consistency between different run periods is useful inside the Collaboration to illustrate the stability of your results, but results should be combined or averaged when shown publicly.
- Have consistent capitalization of your slides' titles.
- Have a consistent font of your choice throughout. A second font is ok, provided both fonts are used consistently. The font size should not be less than 20pt.
- [Guidance](#) on using italic vs. roman fonts for symbols in scientific text. Exceptions to the guidance: e.g., e^+e^-p and e^+Au .
- Title page: add the following for both slides and posters
 - Presenter's name, and "On behalf of the ePIC Collaboration" or "For the ePIC Collaboration"
 - Presenter's institution name and/or logo
 - ePIC logo
 - Conference name, logo (if desired), date and location
 - DOE logo: please add "Supported in part by" above the DOE logo. Use the DOE logo with the text "Office of Science" ([LINK](#)).
 - Logos of the presenter's funding agencies if desired
- Footer/header: add the speaker name, conference name and date, slide number, and/or ePIC logo. Institution name/logo can be added if desired.
- Use bullets not whole sentences. You want the audience listening to you, not trying to read all the text on your slide. The slides are meant to support the narration of the speaker, not make the speaker superfluous.
- Have one intended take-away message for each slide. It should be highlighted in some fashion from the rest of the text on the slide.

- Make figures as large as possible on the slide, considering distances in an auditorium or seminar room.
- Overlay curves if trying to make a point about the effect of different cuts, or background subtractions, etc.
- Multi-panels of plots without text or without writing the point/conclusion of the slide are discouraged.
- Use high quality figures, not low resolution bitmaps.
- If you have more than three figures on a slide you have too many and the audience will not be able to take in all the information.
- If you have more than 1 slide per minute you have too many slides! Your audience is likely seeing your results for the first time and needs time to digest what's plotted before they can digest what the scientific message is.
- Use a standard or abbreviated reference format consistently throughout the presentation. For example, use "Phys. Rev. C 95, 042201 (2017)", "PRC 95, 042201 (2017)", or "arXiv: 1701.08123", but not "<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.95.042201>". You can include an inline link to a webpage, but do not include the text of a URL.
- Acknowledgement: add official ePIC acknowledgements once they become available at the end of the talk.
- Provide supporting details in the backup slides.

Tips for Posters

- If you include your abstract on your poster, it's OK to change it a little to reflect what you are actually going to show, rather than what you hoped to show several months back. If you make a major change to the abstract please make sure that your working group conveners are aware that you have done this. The same goes for the poster title. It's OK to tweak it a little.
- Do not overcrowd your poster with text and figures. People want to browse all the posters and won't be willing to stand there and read what amounts to a long research paper. You should try and convey one or two key messages.
- You can use any font you like, but try to have at most two fonts. The fonts need to be large. A rule of thumb is if you print it out on A4/US letter size paper you should be able to read it easily. If you can't, then when printed on poster size it won't be readable from a few feet away as needs to be if there is a crowd around your poster.
- Have one, and only one, intended take-away message for each section on your poster. It should be highlighted in some fashion from the rest of the text in the section so that a person can take a quick look and be able to tell someone immediately what the key messages are.
- Make figures as large as possible - you can frequently convey a lot more with a figure than you can with a lot of text.
- Use bullets not whole sentences. You want to use the poster to encourage people to discuss your results with you.
- Use high quality figures, not low resolution bitmaps. Remember this is going to be printed out much larger than usual.

Analysis note

A template for composing an analysis note can be found here:

<https://zenodo.org/records/16615353>

Resources

- Presentation tips for scientists:
 - APS Speaker Tips & Guidelines
 - <https://www.aps.org/careers/advice/speaker-tips-guidelines>
 - **Less is more, more is too much: a few tips to improve your talk**
by Kong Tu
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3jd69zicSmo>
 - **Speech, Structure, Slides and Show: The Art and Science of Presentations**
by Zisis Papandreou
 - <https://halldweb.jlab.org/doc-public/DocDB/ShowDocument?docid=4680>

Appendix: Talk Checklist

Checklist for Presentations to Conferences/Workshops^[1]

This form must be submitted with your slides to the Convenor of your Working Group

Presenter's Name:	
Talk Title:	
Conference:	

General Guidelines		✓
I have read the above guidelines	General, Practice Talk and Figure Style Guidelines	
Audience-appropriate	10,000 ft view, methodology, technical level	
Data reference	Follow official naming scheme	
Data details	Minimize info on event selection/cross checks/data periods	
Jargon	No ePIC-specific jargon; limit other jargon	
Figure quality	Clearly labeled/easy to understand	
Figure content	Include supporting text (explanation/conclusions from slide)	
Figure logistics	Axis labels with units; same precision for tick mark labels	
Slide logistics	Slide numbers visible on every slide	
Literature references	Use standard/abbreviated format: PRC 95, 042201 (2017)	
Literature links	Do not show URL text	
Results	Clear about what uncertainties are being shown	
Acknowledgement	"ePIC acknowledges... funding..."	

Practice Talk Guidelines		✓
Presentation	Present talk as at the conference; timing of talk	
Main Slides	Include only conference slides	
Backup Slides	Include slides for discussion of your results	
Plot labelling	Clear labelling (all plots)	
Plot techniques	Overlay curves (acc or sideband subtraction...)	
Discussion	Results will be discussed and vetted	

Supervisor or Convenor name: (check all and initial side box)		
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